

Experiment number 1512

Installation of a mixed forest experiment of European beech, European silver fir, Douglas fir and Norway spruce on sandy outwash plain in central Jutland

Gludsted plantation cps. 52ab, 97c, 142b, 146h and 214c.

December 2025

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Funded by the
European Union

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2 Foreword/Disclaimer

This report is elaborated as part of the MIXFOR project, financially supported by the European Commission. The views and knowledge expressed in this report cannot be considered as the official opinion of the European Commission, nor is it responsible for the use of the information contained in the report.

We are deeply grateful from not only the support from the European Commission (Through the EFI project FORWARDS - The ForestWard Observatory to secure resilience of European forests) but also to the Godfred Birkedal Hartmann Foundation. Without their support, this experiment would not have been possible to install.

3 Summary

This report documents the re-design and establishment of a mixed forest experiment, experiment no. 1512 in the Danish national series of long-term forest experiments. The experiment is located on nutrient-poor, sandy glaciofluvial soils in *Gludsted Plantation*, Central Jutland. The original experiment was initiated in 2000 to study the impact of the shelter density of a Norway spruce shelter on the establishment and development of underplanted European beech (*Fagus sylvatica*), European silver fir (*Abies alba*) and Douglas fir (*Pseudotsuga menziesii*). During 2025 the experiment was transformed into a full-scale **mixed-species thinning experiment**.

The new design investigates the growth and management interactions of the underplanted tree species and of partly underplanted and partly spontaneous naturally regenerated Norway spruce (*Picea abies*). Referring to the original design, these species occur in pure as well as in mixed plots with varying proportions of each species.

The re-designed experiment aims to quantify:

1. The growth performance and stand development of **mixed versus pure stands**.
2. The effects of **two contrasting thinning regimes** (thinning from below and crop-tree thinning, respectively) on tree growth, stand dynamics and species interactions.
3. The influence of species mixture on **soil chemistry** (pH and C:N ratio).
4. The **health** in pure versus mixed stands.

The re-designed layout comprises **five experimental blocks** (four of which are based on the original design and one in a new, pure Douglas fir block), representing contrasting shelter densities and density reduction histories within the range of soil conditions represented in Gludsted Plantation. Installation of the re-designed experiment included the final **shelter tree removal** (in all blocks except one), re-defining and re-marking **plot borders**, a **permanent numbering of individual trees**, **removal of unwanted spontaneously occurring tree species**, and the **initiation of thinning treatments** where stand were sufficiently developed. Measurements were conducted on overstorey trees, understorey trees, soil characteristics and deadwood to document the 'initial' conditions of the re-designed experiment.

The re-designed experiment 1512 represents a critical platform for studying growth, resilience, and management of climate-smart mixed-species forest types in Denmark.

4 Sammenfatning

Denne rapport dokumenterer omlægning og etablering af et **blandingskovforsøg**, forsøg nr. 1512 i den danske nationale serie af langsigtede skovforsøg. Forsøget er placeret på næringsfattige, sandet hedeflade i Gludsted Plantage, Midtjylland. Det oprindelige forsøg blev etableret i 2000 for at undersøge effekten af skærmtæthed fra skærm af rødgran på etablering og udvikling af underplantet bøg (*Fagus sylvatica*), ædelgran (*Abies alba*) og douglasgran (*Pseudotsuga menziesii*). I løbet af 2025 blev forsøget omdannet til et fuldskala **blandskovforsøg med forskellige tyndingsformer**.

Det nye design undersøger vækst og interaktioner mellem de underplantede træarter samt dels underplantet og dels spontant naturligt forynget rødgran (*Picea abies*). Med reference til det oprindelige design forekommer disse arter både i renbestand og i blandskovsparceller med varierende artsandele.

Det omlagte forsøg har til formål at kvantificere:

1. **Vækst og bestandsudvikling** i blanding kontra renbestand.
2. Effekterne af **to kontrasterende tyndingsstrategier** (tynding fra neden og tynding for hovedtræer) på trævækst, bevoksningsdynamik og artsinteraktioner.
3. Blandingskovens indflydelse på **jordkemi** (pH og C:N-forhold).
4. **Sundhedstilstand** i renbestand ift. blanding.

Det omlagte forsøgsdesign omfatter **fem blokke** (fire baseret på det oprindelige design og én ny blok med ren douglasgran) og repræsenterer forskellige tidligere skærmtætheder og tyndingshistorik i

skærmen inden for variationen af jordbundsforhold i Gludsted Plantage. Etableringen af det omlagte forsøg omfatter **hugst af de sidste skærmtræer** (undtagen i én blok), **ny afmærkning af parcellernes grænser**, **permanent nummerering af enkelttræer**, **fjernelse af uønskede spontant forekommende træarter samt igangsætning af tyndingsbehandlinger**, hvor bevoksningerne var tilstrækkeligt udviklede. Der blev gennemført målinger på overstandere, underetagen, jordbundsparametre og dødt ved for at dokumentere de start forholdene i det omlagte forsøg.

Det omlagte forsøg 1512 udgør en central platform til at undersøge vækst, robusthed og forvaltning af klimarobuste blandingskovtyper i Danmark.

5 Background

In recent years, significant efforts have aimed to transfer homogeneous Norway spruce heathland plantations into more resilient, mixed forest types. New suggested species have especially in Denmark been true fir species, Douglas fir and native broadleaves, most often beech (IGN n.d.). Mixed-species forest types are increasingly promoted in order to enhance forest resilience, productivity and biodiversity and, in turn, to mitigate potentially negative impacts of climate change and biotic disturbances. Such procedures form a core component in creating increasingly climate-smart forests of Europe (Alfieri et al. 2025).

Mixtures of ecologically complementary tree species can result in a more efficient use of resources such as light, water, and nutrients, but the effects are highly dependent on the specific species combinations and on local site conditions (Pretzsch et al. 2013, Forrester 2014). On nutrient-poor soils, such as the coarse sands of the relatively uniform glaciofluvial outwash plains covering large areas in Central and Western Jutland, mixing effects are still poorly understood and underexplored.

As of 2024, Denmark had no long-term mixed-forest experiment with replications in this old heathland region¹ (west of the last glacial ice margin) that included both pure and mixed stands for direct comparison.

Beginning in 2000, experiment 1512 was established in Gludsted Plantation to examine the conversion of even-aged, pure stands of Norway spruce into a more stable forest type through the underplanting of a spruce shelterwood with European beech, European silver fir and Douglas fir (Skovsgaard et al. 2004, Brunner et al. 2005, Reventlow et al. 2023). It was originally envisaged that the experiment should continue into a mixed forest experiment based on the underplanted tree species (Brunner et al. 2005).

This new 2025-establishment report presents the transition of experiment 1512 in Gludsted Plantation from a regeneration / conversion experiment into a mixed-species thinning experiment with beech, silver fir, Douglas fir and Norway spruce. Norway spruce was not originally part of the experiment but was possible to include through a combination of additional areas outside the experiment and natural regeneration on areas where original underplanting failed. A pure Douglas fir was originally not a part of the experiment but was possible to incorporate from areas outside the original experiment. The experiment was re-designed to allow for an investigation of long-term effects of species mixtures under different management.

Building on the original design of the experiment (Brunner et al. 2005), the new design incorporates replicated species combinations and thinning treatments across five blocks of different shelter densities and density reduction schemes and different soil characteristics. This unique platform

¹ On better soil there is e.g. the Norway spruce-beech experimental series (see Bryndum 1980, 1982 and Jørgensen 1983).

makes it possible to assess the influence of species mixture on tree growth, stand development, competition (among individual trees of the same or of different species), stem quality and soil properties, thereby potentially providing critical information for developing climate-smart and site-adapted silvicultural strategies in Denmark.

6 Objectives and overall experimental design

The original experiment 1512 investigated the height growth and mortality of beech, silver fir and Douglas fir seedlings planted under a shelter of Norway spruce (Skovsgaard et al. 2004, Brunner et al. 2005, Reventlow et al. 2023).

The re-designed experiment 1512 aims to examine tree and stand growth, tree interactions and stem quality in mixed and pure stands of European beech, European silver fir, Douglas fir and Norway spruce with different proportions of each tree species and subjected to two contrasting thinning regimes, namely thinning from below or thinning for pre-selected potential future crop trees.

Moreover, the experiment aims to examine how species mixtures affect soil chemical properties, particularly pH and C:N ratio, on glaciofluvial outwash soils to quantify belowground responses in different types of mixed forest. Additionally, the experiment can be used to assess the effect of bark stripping by (red) deer on tree growth and stem / timber quality.

6.1 Species combinations

Eight species combinations were included, ranging from pure to two-species mixtures (Table 6.1).

Table 6.1: Overview of tested species combinations.

Combination	Beech (%)	Silver fir (%)	Douglas fir (%)	Norway spruce (%)
1	–	–	–	100
2	50	–	–	50
3	–	–	100	–
4	33	–	66	–
5	100	–	–	–
6	66	33	–	–
7	33	66	–	–
8	–	100	–	–

6.2 Thinning treatments (overview)

Two contrasting thinning treatments are included in the design:

- **Thinning from below.**
- **Thinning for pre-selected potential future crop trees (hereafter simply referred to as crop tree thinning),** involving selective crown release only of pre-selected potential future crop trees.

These treatments were applied across the range of species mixtures; however, not all thinning × species mixture combinations could be replicated due to spatial and resource constraints. A detailed description of the thinning methodology is provided in section 11.5.

6.3 Design structure

The experiment follows a **partial split-split-plot design**:

- **Plot main factor (A):** Species combination (Table 6.1).
- **Subplot factor (B):** Thinning treatment (thinning from below vs. crop tree thinning).
- **Within subplot factor (C): Deer protection** (net vs. no net on stem).

The subplot factor was randomized within blocks. Due to spatial limits, only some A × B combinations are replicated in every block. Nevertheless, the design captures a wide gradient of species interactions and management interventions.

The effects of **shelter density**—no longer an experimental factor — remain visible in the field (as of 2025) and are expected to persist onwards for an unknown period of time.

7 Location of experimental blocks

The experiment is located in Gludsted Plantation, southeast of Ikast and southwest of Silkeborg, Central Jutland, Denmark (Figure 7.1). There are five different experimental blocks located in cps. 52ab (Block 52), 97c (Block 97), 142b (Block 142), 146h (Block 146) and 214c (Block 214). The four most northern blocks were part of the original experiment 1512 (although the exact coverage is not the same, see appendix 16.1 for original blocks) while the small area to the south (Block 146) is a new addition (Figure 7.2).

Figure 7.1 Overview map of location of experiment and its experimental blocks. The major road that crosses through Gludsted plantation from south to north just to the east of the experiment is Main Road 13.

Overall soil conditions are shown in the appendix (16.2). All blocks are located on coarse sandy podzol in flat terrain at 77-90 m elevation. Soil conditions are similar across 4 out of the 5 blocks which are located on the flat “Grindsted Hedeslette” (Grindsted outwash plain). The only deviating block is 97 located in the Kolpensig meltwater valley that runs through the plantation from the east. This is a largely heathland covered area (although many parts are also covered with Norway spruce) that is meandering through the plantation dividing up the orthophoto on Figure 7.2b in a northern and southern part. As has been long known (described by Bryndum 1969, Reventlow et al. 2023 and Rix 1927), this valley deviates from the glaciofluvial meltwater sand in the rest of the plantation and is instead wind dispersed and very homogeneous medium coarse sand². Therefore, Block 97 is even less nutrient rich compared to the other blocks - clearly visible on broadleaf growth and CN ratio in 97 (Reventlow et al. 2023, see also appendix Table 16.1).

² Rix (1927) writes: “After the general deposit of meltwater from the ice sheet, a thin strongly flowing meltwater river emerged eroding through the otherwise flat meltwater deposited plain (Red: Grindsted Hedeslette) causing a valley. Later on, this valley was partly filled with drifting sand with less coarse sand and a more homogeneous distribution of grain size in the sand in the middle range”.

a)

b)

Figure 7.2: Location of all five compartments/blocks that comprise the new experiment across Gludsted plantation on a) topographical map and b) orthophoto background.

Section 8 shows criteria for keeping or removing specific parts of the original experiment 1512 in the new design. Block 146 is only pure Douglas fir and was added specifically because this was lacking in the original experiment design. The provenance in 146 is expected to be comparable to the Douglas fir in the original Experiment 1512 (see Appendix 16.3.2 for provenance elaboration). The location and area for each of the new blocks is shown in Table 7.1.

Table 7.1: Location of each block and as well of a description of its relation to the original experiment.

Block	Easting (m)	Northing (m)	Area (ha)	Relation to original exp. 1512
52	521896	6216602	3.38	App. 40% of original 1512 block included. Additional area outside with pure Norway spruce incorporated.
97	521388	6215466	4.57	Not included in the 2025 measurement campaign as the area was yet developed sufficiently to be transferred to the mixed forest experiment. It might be included later. Almost the entire area of the original 1512 block can potentially be included except a few plots with high mortality.
142	519723	6215167	2.85	App. 50% of original 1512 block included
146	522433	6214158	0.46	New block, only pure Douglas fir
214	517729	6215017	0.58	Only four plots from the original block in 1512 remain. Due to limited funding, it was not included in the 2025 campaign.

8 Criteria for incorporating parts of the original 1512 and delineating new areas.

8.1 Incorporating parts of underplanting from original 1512

Which parts of the original Experiment 1512 (see appendix 16.1 for maps) that could be included was decided based mainly on **sufficient survival of the original underplanting**.

Survival had to be $\geq 60\%$ of the initial underplanting within each underplanted species. Exceptions from this rule occurred where mortality from competition in the underplanting had started (primarily Douglas fir-beech mixture in Block 142) and where the species still covered the area. Furthermore, survival had to be so that no continuous area $> 5 \text{ m} \times 5 \text{ m}$ was dead.

In general, the part of the original Experiment 1512 that could be incorporated coincided where those where there was still shelter in 2024.

In Block 214, most plots were lost to bark beetle attack in 2019; only plots 19–22 (northeastern part) could be retained.

In contrast, nearly all of Block 97 was usable, except plot 13 (dominated by lodgepole pine regeneration) and plots 9 and 23 (windthrow damage).

The western part of Block 52 still retained shelter and was included while the central and eastern part was destroyed, apart from the north central part where beech survival was sufficient.

Block 142 was affected by a combination of bark beetle attacks and wind throw in a patchier fashion than 52. All the Douglas fir/beech part could be incorporated, while survival in the rest of the understory was generally too poor, apart from in plot 41 where practically all the beech had survived but the silver fir had died. Thus, plot 41 changed from beech-silver fir to beech.

Furthermore, mainly plot 40 and a large part of plot 25 changed from beech-silver fir to beech-Norway spruce mixture which will be described in the next section.

8.2 Incorporating Norway spruce in the experimental design

Exceptions to the survival rule occurred where the species in the new experimental design was different compared to the original underplanting experiment. This was only the case for areas where natural regeneration of Norway spruce had taken over the area following mortality in the underplanting (of mainly silver fir and to a smaller degree beech) where Norway spruce was subsequently incorporated in the new experimental design. Either just as Norway spruce or mixed with underplanted beech.

The coverage/distribution rule still applied for delineating Norway spruce plots (no open areas larger than 5 m × 5 m). The goal of the Norway spruce areas was to be as comparable as possible to the underplanted beech (in mixture and the pure stands) in terms of height development/height variation.

Several original beech-silver fir plots (mainly plot 40 and a large part of plot 25) in Block 142 were redesigned according to these procedures to make a mixed Norway spruce-beech plot. What was previously plot 46 (silver fir) in Block 142 could be used as pure Norway spruce.

In Block 52, no Norway spruce areas inside the original block fulfilled the coverage rule. Thus, there was found an area to the east of Block 52 that could be used as pure Norway spruce (Plot K, originally underplanted Norway spruce and silver fir).

Norway spruce was only incorporated in the experimental design of Block 52 and Block 142. Norway spruce regeneration was scarce in Block 97 because of the dense shelter. And in Block 214, the destruction of the shelter happened so late in the process that natural regeneration of Norway spruce has not yet sufficiently established itself.

8.3 Incorporating pure Douglas fir in the experimental design (Block 146)

The criteria for laying out the area with pure Douglas fir was that these areas should be as similar as possible to some of the Douglas fir in Block 142 in terms of height and diameter development, assessed in spring 2024. The Douglas fir in 97 is not representative for Douglas fir in Gludsted plantation or the heathland plantations in general as it is situated in a meltwater valley (see 7) and it was clearly impossible to find a pure Douglas fir reference to this block.

Compartment 146h was the only pure Douglas fir stand in Gludsted Plantation comparable with the Douglas fir-beech mixture in the original Experiment 1512 (mainly Block 142; Block 97 has special site conditions; see Appendix 16.3.2 for provenance details). This block had also originally been planted under shelter, but the shelter had been removed in spring 2023.

8.4 Plot delineation

Plots were extended to rectangular shapes even when tree height at the edge of the stand was different, provided the survival and coverage criteria were met. It is expected that this height difference will be negligible within a few decades.

A strong height gradient within a plot occurred only in plot B in the northern part of Block 146, which was less developed than the southern part. Because Block 146 is small, the entire area was included. The implications of this variation are shown in 13.2.

9 Stand establishment and early measurements

For details on establishment of the underplanting in blocks 52, 97, 142, and 214 see Brunner et al. (2005). Shortly summarized, all blocks (including 146) were deep-plowed before the establishment of the first Norway spruce generation (the overstorey) on former heathland.

In the original experiment 1512, two site preparation methods were used: patch scarification using an excavator that scraped off the 10-15 cm moor layer or strip scarification using a tractor-drawn tine to a depth of 30 cm.

These earlier treatments are now considered to have negligible effect on further stand development and are consequently not discussed further³. Site preparation in the Douglas fir plots in Block 146 was patch scarification using a Kulla cultivator. In the planted Norway spruce in 52 (outside the original Block 52) site preparation was carried out using either a Kulla cultivator or a tractor drawn tine down to 30 cm (same as described for the original 1512).

The underplanting of beech, silver fir and Douglas fir in the original experiment was established at a density of about 4000 trees/ha beneath three different densities of Norway spruce overstorey trees. Planting took place in spring 2000 (blocks 52 and 142) and spring 2002 (blocks 97 and 214).

Douglas fir in Block 146 was planted in 2003 with a planned spacing of 1.75 m × 1.75 m (\approx 3265 plants/ha). Subsequent measurements showed the actual row spacing was closer to 2 m, giving an effective spacing of 1.75 m × 2.0 m and a density of about 2860 plants/ha⁴. Note that these Douglas fir seedlings were container plants unlike in the original experiment 1512 where bareroot seedlings were used.

Naturally regenerated Norway spruce was most likely established mainly around 2005 following a large-scale windthrow and because a subsequent late frost had destroyed parts of the underplanting. Underplanted Norway spruce in Block 52 was planted in 2001; here, too, with the goal of a density of 1.75 m × 1.75 m.

Provenances and planting sizes can be seen in Table 9.1. See the appendix for provenance considerations in regards to the newly added species to the experimental design (appendix 16.3.1 for Norway spruce and 16.3.2 for Douglas fir).

All four blocks of the original 1512 were fenced from the time of planting of the understorey (apart from during windthrow). For blocks 52 and 142, the fence was taken down in 2015, while fences were still standing in blocks 97 and 214 in 2025. The fencing history in 146h remains unknown.

³ If possible, new treatments were laid out across soil preparation treatment otherwise it was not considered.

⁴ There was planted 3000 Douglas fir plants in 146h, and the whole sub compartment h is app. 1.8579 ha, which would equal 1600 plants/ha which is clearly wrong if compared to the result section. Thus, they cannot have been planted across the whole area of h initially. The 2860 trees were estimated given there are 27 rows within plot B, which is 53,9 m long, exactly equally an average distance between rows of 2 m.

Table 9.1: Provenances of the understorey in experiment 1512 and for plantings also plant sizes. Mostly cited directly from Brunner et al. (2005).

Species	Block	Provenance	Plant size
Beech	52, 142 (most plots)	Lundsgård A2625	3/0, 30-50 cm
	142: 39-44	Harager Hegn A2705	3/0, 50-80 cm
	142: Plot 33, 47 and 48	Gråsten A2699	2/0, 40-70cm
	97, 214	Lundsgård A2920	2/0, 30-80 cm
Silver fir	52	Cariglione B5687	2/1s, 10-20 cm
	97, 214	Cariglione B5687	2/3, 25-50 cm
	142	Vilsbøl A2610 ¹	2/2, 10-20 cm
Norway spruce	142	Forsøgsvæsenet ²	-
	52	Forsts planteskole ²	-
	52	Palsgaard F.502 ³	2/2 30-50 cm
Douglas fir	97	Lavereantiere B5456	1/1 20-40 cm
	142	Lavereantiere B5456	2/1, 30-50 cm
	146	Washington B2702	1/0

¹ In the specific plots from the original experiment that continued in the new design.

² Natural regeneration from the shelter stand.

³ Underplanting. Plant size refers to the underplanting.

The original experiment 1512 had been measured in 2000, 2001, 2002 and 2003 (blocks 52 and 142) and in 2000 and 2003 (blocks 97 and 214).

10 Management and measurements until installation of the new mixed forest experiment

For details on management and measurements that occurred after the establishment of the original experiment, we refer to Reventlow et al. (2023). Briefly summarized, the shelter density of the plots was reduced proportionally between the different shelter densities, thus overall keeping the original within-block gradient in shelter density in the overstorey (apart from areas affected by wind throw or bark beetle attack).

After the last of the initial measurements in 2003, Block 142 and Block 52 were not measured again before in 2019, where only the mixed Douglas fir-beech plots were measured in Block 142. Blocks 97 and 214 were measured again in spring 2008 and Autumn 2016.

Apart from the Douglas-fir beech measurements in 142 in 2019 (which was carried out as diameter measurements due to the advanced development of this stand), all **the understorey inventories were carried out using height measurements before the establishment of the new experiment**. For Block 52 in 2019, there was however carried out some corresponding diameter measurements in all plots in 2019 - allowing for the possibility of a height-diameter regression and volume estimation for the 2019 data.

Prior to the establishment of the new mixed forest experiment – ALL measurements in the understorey had been conducted only on the area known as the *net plot area* – the central roughly 25% of the area, see next section on establishing the new experiment for further elaboration.

No thinning intervention in the underplanting have taken place prior to the establishment of the new experiment in 2024. The only reduction in the underplanting has been from mortality arising

especially from bark beetle and wind throw in the overstorey and browsing. Under the remaining shelter, survival in the underplanting was generally high.

11 Installing the re-designed experiment

11.1 Assessing stand readiness: shelter removal and expansion from original net-plot

As a prerequisite for establishing the new mixed forest experiment, it was necessary to assess the readiness of the regeneration across all blocks. The key biological threshold used was whether at least one of the main species on a plot had reached approximately 5 m in height. This threshold guided two critical decisions:

1. Whether the remaining shelter could be removed.
2. Whether measurement should transition from net-plot (25% of plot) to whole plot level.

Where this threshold was met, shelter trees were removed apart from certification trees (blocks 142 and 52 – Block 146 had not no overstorey left) and measurements in the understorey shifted to whole plot scale during the 2024 inventory. Where regeneration was still underdeveloped (blocks 97 and 214), shelter was retained. **Due to limited funding, the understorey/future mixed forest experiment in 97 and 214 was also not measured in the 2024/2025 campaign. The overstorey was measured across all 5 blocks in the 2024/2025 campaign.** In Block 97 and 214, the original shelter markings (e.g. yellow crosses, cf. Brunner et al. 2005) remain in place (although in practice not in Block 214 as remaining area was very small). Whether the original net-plot measurement structure will be kept in Block 97 and 214 depends on when funding for the next measurements can be achieved.

Harvesting of the overstorey was conducted in winter 2026. Because of the uniqueness of the experimental setup, shelter removal was performed with extra care, using high stumps and lifting techniques to protect the understorey. The low **damage levels to the understorey are not representative of typical shelter removal.**

Net-plots to block transitions are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 11.1: Illustrating the measurement concept in 1512's original blocks 52 and 142 relative to the original measurement structure. Originally (2000-2019, left illustration) there was only measured on the net plot area - an area of app. 20m × 20m (the area with red color, app. 25% of the entire original plot area). Now (right illustration) there is measured on the entire original plot area (recall that two original plots are typically merged to form one new plot, attempted to be illustrated here through the open boundary in the bottom visualizing that the plot extend in this case south).

Furthermore, for Block 52, 142 and 214, individual plots were nearly always merged with one adjacent neighboring plot to get large enough areas for implementing thinning treatments (Plots were somewhat smaller in these blocks compared to in Block 97). Positioning of the new thinning treatments followed written criteria ensuring comparable stand development and height across treatments. See 0 in the appendix for an elaborate description of how this was done.

11.2 Tree and row numberings

Individual numbering was always starting from the southwest corner proceeding towards east in a snake-wise alternative pattern (single row measurement, “enkelt rækker” in Danish). This was simple to apply in planted areas that had not been measured before and thus had no net plots (pure Douglas fir in Block 146). It was more complicated in the other parts of the experiment which will be described in the following subsection.

11.2.1 Areas with former net plot measurements

In the process of transitioning from the net-plot to the whole plot area (including the merging of former plots), the numbering was changed so that the trees on the sample plot previously measured on the net plots would receive a new row number and new row tree relative to the whole plot level. Thus, the row that had been row 1 in the original net plot measurements could e.g. be row number 7 now. Importantly, the new measurements were made to fit the original measurement order/direction in the original Experiment 1512. What this means is that i.e. Row 1 in the original net plot was always, and continues to be, measured from south to north. Thus, to establish the right measurement direction for the new rows measured for the first time and located west of the net plot the number of rows to the west had to be counted. If this number was uneven, then the measurement direction in the first row started from the north to fit the snake-wise alternating pattern).

In the cases where two original plots were merged together in east-western direction (e.g. plot A in 52 which covers both the original plot 1 and 16), the measurement direction pattern dictated from plot 1 (the western plot) was kept until reaching the row that contained the net plot in the original plot 16 – then starting from the south (even if the row before had also started from the south).

If trees were forking (smallest leader had a steep angle and >50% of the diameter of the main leader) then they were noted as two trees (as standard in IGN’s long-term experiments). This sometimes changes the number and order of trees inside the net plot compared to previous measurements (where the concept of planting no. rather than row tree number had been used).

The original numbering in the net plot was two additional separate columns in the data structure, and this link was kept (one column denoting net plot row number and another net plot row tree number). A dummy variable named net plot was also introduced in the data structure.

11.2.1.1 Mixtures of beech and Norway spruce

Mixtures of beech and Norway spruce always had net plots but were a special case because natural regeneration of Norway spruce had been added to the plot.

In the mixtures of underplanted beech and natural regeneration of Norway spruce, the row structure in the underplanting was kept. Meaning that the underplanted rows of beech was used as a baseline for the measurement structure. Norway spruce trees were attributed to the existing row structure dependent on their position. This slightly depended on the block due to the circumstances behind the emergence of the Norway spruce regeneration.

11.2.1.1.1 Block 52

Mixed Norway spruce-beech in Block 52 was originally only beech. In Block 52, Norway spruce located to the west of the original beech row or completely on that beech row, e.g. row 2, received the row number of this beech rows. Only one Norway spruce tree was kept and marked with blue spray for each 1.6 m × 1.6 m space between the beech rows, the remaining Norway spruce was removed. Figure 6.2 attempts to explain this concept. This way of measuring naturally meant that order within in the net plot trees changed because Norway spruce trees was added in between.

Figure 11.2 Illustration of the principle for assigning row numbers to Norway spruce trees in the beech-Norway spruce mixture in Block 52 (which originally was only planted beech).

11.2.1.1.2 Block 142

Mixed Norway spruce- beech in Block 142 was originally beech-silver fir (2 rows beech and 1 row silver fir). In Block 142 almost all rows of silver fir had entirely perished in 2024, and the setting was therefore different to Block 52.

In the 1.6 m × 1.6 m area between the existing beech rows, there was used a similar approach to Block 52. However, when reaching the areas where there was one row of silver fir the approach is different. Here, an area of 3.2 m × 1.6 m is designated for each row tree (the distance between the two beech rows that provide the stand structure), where the tallest spruce was marked with blue spray, and the remaining trees were removed (Figure 11.3). The tallest Norway spruce in this former silver fir row is marked as described above, and the rest are removed. In this selection (the space where there was formerly silver fir), slightly more attention is given to precise location than when selecting the remaining Norway spruce trees in the 1.6 m × 1.6 m spaces between two beech rows to reduce the area of open space. As far as possible, the remaining tree is placed in the middle of the former silver fir row, unless another tree is significantly larger.

Figure 11.3 Illustration of the principle for assigning row numbers to Norway spruce trees in the beech-Norway spruce mixture in Block 142 (which originally was beech-silver mixture where practically all silver fir had died following the destruction of the overstorey back in 2005).

11.2.1.2 Pure Norway spruce

It was also managed to fit the measurements of pure Norway spruce into a row-wise measuring system. In Block 52, it was structured around the underplanted rows of Norway spruce that could be found in the regeneration (and was a much more important component of the stand than the natural regeneration that later emerged, and were thus smaller, where the initially planted silver fir had perished). It was managed to connect all trees remaining at the time of measurement to this row structure due to the combined effect of the pruning and the removal of natural regeneration to promote access (both was conducted before measurements, see 11.4).

For Block 142, this was also managed due to the structuring created by the pruning and access related thinning, despite that no Norway spruce in this plot was planted in rows (all was natural regeneration).

11.3 Plot marking

Galvanized magnetic iron pipes were hammered down in each corner of the individual plots in summer 2025, and coordinates were taken with a differential GPS (precision within a few cm). Two pipes were hammered down to mark a corner boundary between two plots if there was a skidding road that made up the boundary where there was placed an iron pipe on each side of the skidding road. As a rule, the iron pipe was hammered down in the center between the outer and the inner row (leaving the outer rows as border trees both in the east-west and north south perspective). A white 1.5 m high plastic stick was inserted into the iron pipe.

The area inside the iron pipes is considered the main plot. The outer planting row beyond the iron pipe was considered border zone (outside of main plot, "UB" in data) but were still measured⁵. All

⁵ The Norway spruce plot in Block 52, plot K was not measured outside of the main plot in the 2025 measurement.

trees within the corner iron pipes are registered in the experiment. Overstorey trees are also measured if they are standing in the border zone (to allow link to the old measurements on the overstorey which originally were not outlined by iron pipes but by the colored crosses on the overstorey trees).

If the border was made up of regeneration of the same species combination or of different species combinations, then there was put in one iron pipe to mark a common boundary where no buffer zone was necessary.

Within the border of the plots there were still skidding tracks present and thus, some planting rows located adjacent to these. These were not considered border trees in the strictest sense (still included in e.g. basal area calculation) but they could not be considered trees truly representative for that thinning treatment. Thus, a new variable “Spor” (“road tree”) was implemented in the experimental design, see also later chapter on measurements.

Note that the old, galvanized iron pipes marking the net plot area from the original Experiment 1512 in Block 97, 142, 214 and Block 52 (not including the Norway spruce plot K which is outside of the original experiment) are still present in the stand, which can result in confusion in regard to plot boundaries. Similarly, a varying number of plastic sticks marking the beginning and end of the net plot rows are also present (red sticks marking the start and end of the uneven rows in the net plot rows, and the black sticks the even rows). Most of these sticks were still present in 2024/2025 to aid in orientation (sometimes overgrown with moss), but many were also lost or overgrown by moss.

11.4 Access preparation and species removal

11.4.1 Access-related thinning/pruning

Firstly, natural regeneration was removed on all skidding roads in Block 52, 142 and 146 in autumn 2024. This was also the case in the plots where the natural regeneration was the same as the target species on the plot (Norway spruce plots).

In the pure Norway spruce plots in Block 52 and 142, it was in many areas not possible for the measuring team to access the stand due to very high density in Autumn 2024. Thus, the natural regeneration was put out on 1 m × 1 m distance with a chainsaw (this thinning was not accounted for in the measurement as it was naturally done before the measurement). In Block 52, the Norway spruce treatment was a planted Norway spruce stand supplemented with natural regeneration, and this pre-measurement thinning was only conducted in the naturally regenerated parts.

To further increase access to the stand, all rows of 52,142 and 146 were on one side pruned to 2m height by a forest worker with a chain saw (pruning to both sides in every second space between the rows, so each row was pruned on either eastern or western side) during autumn 2024 or spring 2025.

11.4.2 Species removal

11.4.2.1 Before measurement

In the pruning action described above for 52, 142 and 146, the instruction to the forest worker was also to remove all non-target species (species that the plot was not defined for in the design) that the person came across. **This removed most non-target species on the plots before the measurement team came into the stand to save time on measurements**, but the person did not look through the entire plot making sure that every non-target tree was removed. This removal of other species was not accounted for as there were generally only small quantities of other species present.

An exception was in the pure Douglas fir treatment in 146h plot B, where there was a larger proportion of other tree species than expected when the stand was originally selected (the stand ended up extended further to the north to have as much area/data as possible where the stand was a bit more uneven). Thus, the removal of these non-target species in Block 146 plot B did end up constituting a large volume. Since this removal of unwanted species by the forest worker was conducted before measurement, this left a knowledge gap in terms of how much that had been removed from the stand. To remedy this, there was in the four circular taxation plots of radius 4 m used for assessing thinning requirements (see section 11.5.1.1), also measured stumps to quantify the thinning intensity from the removal of unwanted species. This thinning constituted app. 6 m²/ha and app. 2500 trees per ha, thus mainly small trees (Dg app. 5.5 cm). The removal was in practice small Norway spruce and larger larch.

In Block 97 there was a specific problem with dense lodgepole pine regeneration in selected plots, and practically all of this was removed in autumn 2024/spring 2025.

11.4.2.2 *During measurement*

After the forest worker had opened up the stand and removed most-non-target species, the remaining/forgotten part of the non-target species in 52, 142 and 146 were selected for thinning by the measuring team when they measured the actual stand in autumn 2024/spring 2025 (and accounted for in the results, see Table 13.11) and **removed– unless the removal would cause large openings (larger than 5 m × 5 m)**. Thus, there are still some non-target species left after thinning on Table 13.11. It is important to note that non-target trees were also in the crop tree thinning even if they were not standing next to a main crop tree.

11.5 Implementation of thinning treatments

A further thinning was carried out within the target species of the experiment (to accelerate stand development of the target species) in blocks 146, 142 and 52 as these blocks, by 2024, had a more advanced development than others (practically all these plots were at least 5 m tall).

Thinning treatments were allocated to plots at random. The thinning treatment was installed in Block 52 in spring 2025 by a forest worker with a chain saw (the plots were not that developed yet and no commercial products were removed from the stand). In contrast, it was installed in Block 142 and 146 in autumn 2025 using a feller buncher where commercial products were removed from the stand.

The procedure for laying out the thinning treatments is described in appendix 16.4.

11.5.1 Description of thinning treatments

The experiment includes two contrasting thinning treatments: thinning from below and crop tree thinning (thinning for pre-selected potential future crop trees). The key difference between the two methods is that with crop tree thinning, thinning is carried out to promote only the pre-selected potential future crop trees.

11.5.1.1 *Thinning from below*

Thinning from below should predominantly favor dominant trees more or less evenly distributed over the stand by removing other types of trees. Thinning from below aims to follow this order of priority for tree removal:

1. Removal of wolf trees.
2. Spacing: Trees growing close to trees of larger stem or crown diameter are removed regardless of whether or not they qualify as crop trees.
3. Diameter and height: Trees reaching into the crown of taller trees are removed.

4. Damaged trees: Bark-stripped trees may be removed unless their removal creates an excessively large gap.

No special consideration should be given to pre-selected potential future crop trees (see 11.5.2) apart from ensuring that they are not removed.

At future thinning interventions, the residual basal area of each plot treated with thinning from below should remain at around the basal area of the classical growth models of Henriksen (1957), Karlberg (1961) and Møller (1933) for European silver fir, Douglas fir and Norway spruce, respectively, and for all species referring to site class 3 of the relevant model / yield table. For beech, the basal area should expectedly stay at around 2/3 of that of the model for beech by Møller (1933), site class 3. In mixed plots, the proportion of beech by basal should remain around 50 percent of the original proportion of beech by stem number, reflecting the substantially larger growth capacity of the conifers in these plots. Should the growth development turn out to be stronger or weaker than expected, the target basal areas should be modified accordingly.

More elaborated examples:

Mixed stand of Douglas fir (Hg = 15.5 m) and beech (Hg = 8 m).

In pure stands, Douglas fir at Hg 15.5 m corresponds to a post-thinning basal area of 27.5 m²/ha, while beech at Hg 8 m corresponds to 15.6 m²/ha.

Given that beech occupies one third of the original planting density, its share should be one sixth of the pure-stand basal area:

$$15.6 / 6 = 2.6 \approx \mathbf{3 \text{ m}^2/\text{ha}}.$$

Douglas fir then accounts for the remaining five sixths:

$$27.5 \times 5/6 = 22.9 \approx \mathbf{23 \text{ m}^2/\text{ha}}.$$

The mixed stand should therefore have a total basal area of $\approx \mathbf{26 \text{ m}^2/\text{ha}}$ after thinning.

Pure beech stand (Hg = 8.0 m).

A pure stand at this height corresponds to a basal area of 15.6 m²/ha after thinning.

Adjusting to two thirds of full density gives $\approx \mathbf{10.4 \text{ m}^2/\text{ha}}$ after thinning.

Pure Norway spruce stand (Hg = 10.3 m).

A pure stand at this height corresponds to $\mathbf{25.3 \text{ m}^2/\text{ha}}$ after thinning.

However, to initiate the experimental thinning treatment, there was initially thinned somewhat harder than this in the 2024-2025 thinning (wolf trees were not targeted as highest priority in this thinning). In 2024/2025 the stem number of each species is reduced to fit a specific height and relative tree distance (RTD, same RTD used for all species on the plot) for the development stage.

RTD is equal to:

$$\text{RTD} = \frac{\sqrt{1000/Nha}}{H}$$

, where Nha= stem number per ha and H is stand height, where Hg (height of average basal area tree) is typically used.

The less development there is, then there is thinned to a higher RTD, meaning in principle heavier thinning. As development stage was quite different across blocks, the exact thinning procedure for each block is described below.

Block 52

For Block 52 we had measurements from spring 2019 for the net plots with estimates of stem number and heights. We extracted the 50 highest trees per net plot across both species due to the intimate mixing and taking mixing proportion into account. E.g. for a 2/3 silver fir 1/3 beech stand, the height of the 34 highest silver fir and 17 highest beeches were extracted. Each net plot was app. 25 m × 25m ~ 625 m², corresponding to the 800 highest trees per ha. This height extraction was used as an estimate for Hg in such a young stand. Assuming no mortality, there was “modelled” forward to winter 2024 using 50 cm height growth per year growth for 2019-2025. Annual height growth of 50 cm was used since the stand was too young to be adequately predicted using the forest modelling tool Vidar.

This resulted in a RTD of on average 0.26 (0.21-0.30) on the plot level (across all low thinned plots and both species) before thinning after the 2024 growing season. It was decided to thin to a stem number for the target species of app. 3000 trees/ha as this was operationally simple and corresponded with a reduction to an average RTD of 0.28 (0.24-0.31).

This thinning selection was generally conducted based on a 2 × 2 trees system - walking through the stand between two rows and for every two row trees in each row, selecting one of the trees in this 2 × 2 matrix for thinning, reducing to app. 75% of original planting number. For Block 52, this was done across species on the plots because the mixing was so intimate (row by row mixing). It was sought to keep the original mixing percentage from the planting after the thinning.

Block 142

For Block 142, there was also extracted the 50 highest trees from the net plot measurements in 2019. The only plots in Block 142 where thinning from below was implemented was Douglas fir-beech mixtures - here it was based on the 33 highest Douglas fir and the 17 highest beeches on the net plot. Unlike in Block 52, there was used species-specific plot height estimates – not just plot estimates, because of the large difference in development between Douglas fir and beech and the less intimate mixing of the species compared to in Block 52 (4 rows Douglas fir followed by two beech rows). This species-specific height was used to represent Hg in 2019. Based on the site index that fitted this species-specific height-age relation, Hg was modelled forward for the next 6 years using Vidar. This resulted in RTD for beech from 0.14 (eastern part of 142, light), to 0.16 (center, middle dense) to 0.35 (west, dense). For Douglas fir, the similar RTD across Block 142 before thinning was 0.12, 0.14 and 0.21. To make thinning operational, it was decided to thin to a RTD of:

- 0.24 (very heavy thinning) for western part of Block 142 (dense shelter in original experiment)
 - o 2/5 of the original planting number after thinning for Douglas fir
 - o No thinning necessary for beech
- 0.23 (heavy thinning) for middle part of Block 142 (medium shelter in original experiment)
 - o 2/5 left of original planting number after thinning for beech
 - o 1/4 left of original planting number after thinning for Douglas fir
- 0.22-0.23 (heavy thinning) for eastern part of Block 142 (medium shelter in original experiment)
 - o 1/3 left of original planting number after thinning for beech
 - o 1/5 left of original planting number after thinning for Douglas fir

Based on this, there was not thinned for beech in the thinning from below plots in the dense part of 142 in 2024/2025 (RTD already >0.24), but there was thinned in all other species-plot combinations for thinning from below plots in Block 142.

The actual thinning was implemented on larger scale in Block 142 compared to in Block 52 because of the much larger mortality (Block 142 was much more developed) in Block 142 from competition/self-thinning (Figure 11.4). Without going in detail, the procedure involved counting the number of rows of each species and then estimating the number of trees that should be present in each row which was then implemented by going through the stand on a 2-4 row basis (all rows for the same species at a time so 2 for beech and 4 for Douglas fir).

Figure 11.4: Overview of the system for selecting beech and Douglas fir for thinning **in thinning from below treatment** in mixed plots of Douglas fir-beech in Block 142 in the 2025 thinning, showing how thinning is implemented separately for the two species based on the specific mixing row structure – two rows for beech and 4 rows for Douglas fir. Specific thinning intensity visualized is an example. Blivende = remaining, tynding = thinning, dødt træ = dead tree, douglasgran=Douglas fir, bøg=beech.

Block 146

In 146, there were no previous measurements. To assess stem number reduction need in Douglas fir plot B (after the unwanted species had been removed), there was created four sample plots with 4 m radius – one in each corner of the stand. The height of the two thickest trees in each sample plot was measured, and the stem number was counted. The average of these 8 tree heights was found and the total stem number multiplied with 50 to find stems/ha. Based on these estimates (stem number $\approx 900/\text{ha}$, height ≈ 9.8 m) RTD in the present stand was calculated to be 0.34.

Thus, although the stand had appeared dense when initially selected to be part of the new experiment, there ended up having been removed a large quantity of other species in the plots here (as mentioned in section 11.4.1). As a consequence, based on the circular sample plots mentioned in 11.4.1, it was chosen not to thin additionally within Douglas fir as RTD after the unwanted species removal was already much higher than 0.22.

The above are just the procedure and the estimates for what was the goal with the thinning operation when the thinning treatment was initiated. For details of the **actual thinning** conducted in 2024/2025 in Block 52, 142 and 146, see section 13.2.

11.5.1.2 Crop tree thinning

Crop tree thinning was implemented as first choice when the number of plots available was too few (or that the area with a particular species combination was too little) to have space to install both

thinning treatments. For example, limitations in area meant that Norway spruce and mixtures of Norway spruce and beech had to be subjected to crop tree thinning throughout the experiment.

The crop tree thinning was originally designed to release **200 designated potential future crop trees per ha**, so that it would be unlikely that there would be crown contact between a crop tree and any competitor within the following 5 years after thinning. This would correspond to at least 1 m of open space ('blue ring') between the crop tree crown and any competitor tree crown after thinning.

In practice, this was slightly altered both regarding crop tree numbers but also regarding the size of the blue ring radius:

Block 52: Due to some misunderstanding, the crop tree thinning in Block 52 ended up being somewhat less intensive than above mentioned. Instead, **crop tree thinning in Block 52 was carried out for trees that touched the crop tree's branches in the crown**. This deviation from the arranged procedure was not a major issue, as given the developmental stage, it was somewhat premature to initiate thinning in nearly all of Block 52, apart from in the Norway spruce plot K.

Block 142 and 146: In Block 142 and 146, a thinning for 200 future trees would have resulted in an overly heavy thinning in most of the plots (given the development stage where the plots had never been thinned before and had required thinning for some time). Thus, in all of Block 142 and 146, there ended up being thinned for only 100 crop trees/ha (1 crop tree for every 10 m × 10 m). This is in line with the expected future reduction in crop trees.

11.5.2 Crop tree selection protocol

Crop trees were selected not only in the crop tree thinning, but also in the thinning from below treatment to allow for a comparison of treatments in the future. **One primary crop tree was selected for every 10 m × 10 m. One secondary crop tree was also selected for every 10 m × 10 m area in the crop tree thinning treatment in Block 52** (so that there could be thinned for 200 potential future trees per ha in Block 52). **A secondary crop tree was naturally not selected in Blocks 142 and 146 as these included only thinning for 100 pre-selected crop trees per ha (see description in the previous section)**.

Crop trees were selected during the winter of 2024/2025 prior to thinning among the remaining shelter trees in the overstorey.

The way it was done in practice was that there were selected 4(8) trees within each 20 m × 20 m area (20m is app. equal to the distance between the middle of a skidding road to the middle of the next skidding road). The total plot area did not always fit with the subplot grid structure, and there were then selected a few crop trees in the outer periphery, according to the area that was missing from applying the full grid quadrants.

Crop trees were selected according to the following criteria (mentioned in order of priority):

For **all conifers**:

- 1: Even spatial distribution (on average aiming for approximately 10 m between crop trees, but in no case less than 7 m or more than 14 m).
- 2: Large crown / stem diameter.
- 3: No bark stripping damage (neither old nor new).
- 4: Small branch diameter.

For beech:

- 1: Even spatial distribution (on average aiming for approximately 10 m between crop trees, but in no case less than 7 m or more than 14 m).
- 2: No forking (branching out of the crown) below 6 m above ground level.
- 3: Large crown / stem diameter.
- 4: Straight stem.
- 5: No tilting stem.
- 6: Long clear bole.

The additional crop tree per 10 m × 10 m in the crop tree thinning was selected according to the same criteria but at least 5 m away from any other crop tree.

In the mixed stands, the aim was a similar number of crop trees within the individual tree species as the percentage of that species at planting of the original experiment. To make it easy, there was started from the southwest corner and worked through each 20 m × 20 m cell. In plots assigned to e.g. 66% silver fir and 33 % beech, minimum 1 and maximum two of the four 10 m × 10 m cells within each 20 m × 20 m cell could be stocked with beech (reaching approximately 33% in the overall selection). Eventually, some parts of the plots ended up having crop trees more grouped by species. There were also plots that diverged somewhat between the species distribution in the crop tree selection and representation on the plot (see 13.2.4).

Primary crop trees were marked with two rings at breast height, while secondary crop trees (only relevant in the crop tree thinning in Block 52) were marked with one ring at breast height. Crop trees were marked with different color dependent on the thinning treatment. Crop trees in “Thinning for crop trees” was marked with yellow paint, while crop trees in “Thinning from below” was marked with white paint.

11.6 Crop tree deer protection

Deer often strongly fray and bark strip newly released crop trees. To prevent or, at least, reduce fraying and bark stripping a **deer protection net (“Poly-Net Skrællebeskyttelsesnet”)** was put onto every other primary crop tree, protecting the basal stem to approximately 2 m above ground level. This was done in the thinning from below treatment as well as in the crop tree treatment across Block 52, 142 and 146. Only doing it on every second primary crop tree will allow a subsequent analysis of bark stripping damages on released crop trees. The statistical design of this part of the experiment is similar to a split-plot design.

Selection of crop trees for net mounting was conducted using the data collection file after the initial measurement where every second primary crop tree for each species in the data file was selected for net protection.

11.7 Map overview of plot layout and treatments

This section provides two different types of maps of the new experiment. For the blocks that are part of the original 1512 (Blocks 52 and 142), conceptual figures (not to scale) are provided for each of these plots in relation to the original experiment (Figure 11.5 and Figure 11.9). These conceptual figures are also provided for the two blocks 97 and 214 that were not yet ready for installation of the mixed forest experiment / thinning treatments. For all blocks, precise georeferenced maps are also included (Figure 11.6, Figure 11.10, Figure 11.11).

Figure 11.5: Conceptual illustration of the new Block 52, displayed in a similar format to the original Block 52 illustration in appendix Figure 16.1 to illustrate the linkage. The illustration is not to scale. The tree species text in the west denotes the originally planted species combination eastwards. When the planted species combination is not equal to the species combination in the new Experiment 1512 (in Block 52 only the case for plot J, and of course plot K which was outside the original experiment), the actual, present species combination in the new experiment is written on the plot. Orange dotted lines denote skidding roads. Gradient of gray denotes which shelter density gradient the plot originally belonged to (dark gray =dense, medium-dark gray =medium shelter). EB=beech. SF=silver fir, DF=Douglas fir, NS= Norway spruce. TB= Thinning from below. TC=Crop tree thinning. P=patch-wise. S=strip-wise.

Figure 11.6: Map of Block 52 with all the experimental treatment in the new version of the experiment. EB= European beech. SF=silver fir. NS=Norway spruce. TB= thinning from below. TC= Crop tree thinning.

		Shelter density					
		Dense		Medium		Open	
Tree species combination	EB /SF	4 Fut. TC	5 Fut. TB	12 Fut. TC		20 Fut. TB	21 Fut. TC
	SF /EB	3 Fut. TB	6 Fut. TC	11 Fut. TC	14 Fut. TB	19 Fut. TB	22 Fut. TC
	SF	2 Fut. TB	7 Fut. TC	10 Fut. TC	15 Fut. TB	18 Fut. TC	
	DF /EB	1 Fut. TB	8 Fut. TC		16 Fut. TC	17 Fut. TB	24 Fut. TC
		P	S	P	S	P	S
Soil preparation (Patch/Strip)							

Figure 11.7: Conceptual illustration of the new Block 97, displayed a similar format to the original Block 97 illustration in appendix Figure 16.1 to illustrate the linkage. The illustration is not to scale. The tree species text in the west denotes the originally planted species combination eastwards which are in Block 97 always equal to the species in the new experimental design (apart from the white areas that were taken out because of too high mortality in the underplanting). Gradient of gray denotes which shelter density gradient the plot originally belonged to (dark gray =originally dense, medium-dark gray =originally medium, light gray =originally open shelter). EB=beech. SF=silver fir, DF=Douglas fir. TB= Thinning from below. TC=crop tree thinning. P=patch-wise. S=strip-wise. Thinning treatment are not installed yet in 2025 (thus "Fut." For "future")

Figure 11.8: Map of Block 97 with all the experimental treatment in the new version of the experiment. Green dots denote locations for deadwood sampling. EB= European beech. SF=silver fir, DF=Douglas fir. TB= thinning from below. TC= Crop tree thinning. Thinning treatments are not installed yet in 2025 (thus “Fut.” For “future”)

Figure 11.9: Conceptual illustration of the new Block 142, displaying a similar format to the original Block 142 illustration in appendix Figure 16.1 to illustrate the linkage. The illustration is not to scale. The tree species text in the west denotes the originally planted species combination eastwards. When the planted species combination is not equal to the species combination in the new Experiment 1512 (due to silver fir mortality), the actual, present species combination in the new experiment is written on the plot. Gradient of gray denotes which shelter density gradient the plot originally belonged to (dark gray equal originally dense, medium-dark gray equal originally medium, light gray equal originally open shelter). Plot G is located both in the originally open and medium shelter area but is shown only in light gray for simplicity. EB=beech. SF=silver fir, DF=Douglas fir, NS= Norway spruce, TB= Thinning from below. TC=crop tree thinning. P=patch-wise. S=strip-wise.

Figure 11.10: Map of Block 142 with all the experimental treatment in the new version of the experiment. Green dots denote locations for deadwood sampling. EB= European beech. SF=silver fir, DF=Douglas fir. NS= Norway spruce. TB= thinning from below. TC= Crop tree thinning.

Figure 11.11 Map of Block 146. DF=Douglas fir. TB= thinning from below. TC= Crop tree thinning.

Figure 11.12 Conceptual illustration of the new Block 214, displayed a similar format to the original Block 214 illustration in appendix Figure 16.1 to illustrate the linkage. The illustration is not to scale. The tree species text in the west denotes the originally planted species combination eastwards which are in Block 214 always equal to the species in the new experimental design. Gradient of gray denotes which shelter density gradient the plot originally belonged to (light gray equal originally open shelter). EB=beech. SF=silver fir. Fut. TC= Crop tree thinning to be implemented in the future. P=patch-wise. S=strip-wise. Thinning treatments are not installed yet in 2025 (thus "Fut." For "future")

Figure 11.13 Map of Block 214. EB=Beech. SF=silver fir. Fut. TC= Crop tree thinning to be implemented in the future.

12 Tree and stand variables for measurement

Measurements were conducted on the overstorey, the understorey, deadwood and for soil chemistry during 2024-2025.

12.1 Overstorey

The overstorey was calipered for all 5 plots in winter 2024/2025. The overstorey was cross calipered (both between east-west and north-south) in all blocks (Block 146 had no remaining overstorey trees). Status was registered as either live or dead and if it was lying or standing (stumps were not measured) and any damages were noted.

The location of the overstorey tree in terms of the new plot in the mixed forest experiment as well as the original plot in 1512 was registered (only applies to Block 214, 142 and 52). Overstorey trees were measured also if they were standing outside of the new main plot (the area inside the iron pipes) – in the outer border row, (in Danish: “rand”). An example would be if a tree was standing outside the new plot A in Block 52 but had been within the original plot 1. This was to ensure the link to previous measurement of the overstorey (which has previously been measured on the entire stocked area known as “brutto-parcel” which also included the outer border row). In the data, it was noted if trees were standing in or outside of the iron pipes.

One random overstorey tree per **original plot** (meaning two per plot in Block 52 and 142) was measured for also height, crown diameter, crown height (first **crown forming branch**), defoliation (see appendix 16.6 on how to measure this variable). The 2024 measurement is the last time the overstorey must be measured apart from in Block 97 due to its delayed development.

12.2 Understorey

The understorey in Block 97 and 214 (plots that were mainly <5 m high) was not measured in the 2024/2025 measurement year.

The work took longer than anticipated, meaning that the measuring unfortunately had to be carried out well into the growing season of 2025. Exact time of measurement is evident from Table 12.1.

Table 12.1 Exact time of measurement of understorey of individual plots.

Time of measurement	Block 52	Block 142	Block 146
Measured before May 2025	All plots		
May 2025		F, J	
Ultimo May to ultimo June 2025		H	
Ultimo May to primo July 2025	-	A, D, E, K	
June 2025	-	B	A, B
Ultimo July to medio August 2025	-	G	-
August 2025	-	I	-

The understorey was measured according to the measurement structure outlined in 11.2. Thus, row number, row direction and row tree number were registered. Measurements were connected to original net plot measurements on the underplanting from the original 1512 (net plot row and planting position). This was naturally not possible for block 146 and for the two pure Norway spruce plots (Plot I in Block 142 and K in Block 52) as these areas/species had never been measured.

Diameter at breast height (DBH) between east-west side (and cross calipered if >10 cm), tree species and status (Live, dead standing, dead lying, missing, marked for thinning) was noted, any old or new bark stripping damages (registered as “1” if it only had an old damage, and “2” if it had a new

damage) as well as whether it was positioned out towards a skidding road was noted. As already mentioned, forks (steep angle and smallest at least 50% of the diameter of the larger) below 1.3 m were counted as two trees. **Dead trees were not calipered in the 2025 starting measurement for naturally regenerated Norway spruce, as this would have been too much work.**

If underplanted tree height was less than 1.3 m then height was measured (not DBH). **Naturally regenerated trees (i.e. Norway spruce) below 1.3 m height was not measured.**

Furthermore, according to a systematic pattern, there was chosen six height trees per species per **new** plot where there was measured height, crown height, crown diameter and defoliation. Height trees were also noted in the data collection to be re-found in later measurements. These variables were also measured for **all primary crop trees, where it was also noted if it had net protection against bark stripping. The secondary crop trees in the crop tree thinning in Block 52 were not measured for these extra variables.** It was for all crop trees noted that it was a crop tree (and if it was secondary or primary).

12.3 Other variables

12.3.1 Soil variables

The C/N ratio and pH were measured in Block 52 across the span of various mixing percentages with beech and silver fir and Norway spruce (see Table 12.2). More precisely: it is done in:

Dense shelter: silver fir, silver fir mixed with beech, beech mixed with silver fir, beech.

Medium shelter: Pure beech, Norway spruce mixed with beech.

Furthermore, it is done in the Norway spruce regeneration area and in the Old Norway spruce plantation (north of experiment, similar age as the overstorey in the experiment). The goal of this soil chemistry sampling is to see how the soil develops as conversion progresses.

This soil sampling was conducted app. in the direct center of each original treatment, unless this is on a skidding track, then the measuring placed is moved to the northeast until it is 1 m into the stand (see Table 12.2 for exact coordinates). The measuring place is marked with a false acacia stick. Soil extraction is done with a soil auger that is hammered down at least three different places (within 0.5 m around the marking) to extract the soil.

On each measuring place, there is measured CN and pH in three different depths (0-30, 30-60, 60-90 cm). Thus, in total 39 samples are extracted for each of CN and pH. Samples were taken in spring February 2025.

All these soil results, along with results from the other blocks collected in 2019 are shown in the appendix (16.2).

Table 12.2: Coordinates in decimal degrees for soil sampling for pH and CN along a mixing gradient in Block 52. Block 146 was also included for general site mapping purposes, as there had not previously been soil sampled in this block.

Plot	Species	Soil preparation	Dec_deg_north (°)	Dec_deg_east (°)
A	Silver fir	Patch	56.0930461	9.3510969
A	Silver fir	Stripe	56.0929259	9.3515731
C	Silver fir-beech	Patch	56.0936949	9.3513672
C	Silver fir-beech	Stripe	56.0936547	9.3519123
E	Beech-silver fir	Patch	56.0943508	9.3516307
F	Beech-silver fir	Stripe	56.0943309	9.3521601
G	Beech	Patch	56.0951563	9.3519961
G	Beech	Stripe	56.0950048	9.3530563
I	Beech	Patch	56.0949418	9.3530636
J	Beech-Norway spruce	Stripe	56.0948151	9.3536803
K	Norway spruce	-	56.0928729	9.3556269
Norway spruce plantation 1 (north of Block 52)	Norway spruce (overstorey)	-	56.0957902	9.3520575
Norway spruce plantation 2 (north of Block 52)	Norway spruce (overstorey)	-	56.0956793	9.3528182
Block 146 (Dgr, plot A)	Douglas fir	-	56.07260	9.36010

12.3.2 Dead wood

Deadwood was measured within a circular plot with a radius of 15 m. There was sampled deadwood in one sample plot for every ha of the experiment (including areas where the understorey was not measured in 2024-2025). The position of these plots is randomly selected to fit UTM coordinates ending with “00” for both north and east coordinate (thus, 100 m × 100 m grid net). The exception to this rule was in Block 52 and 146 where it was done on the same locations as the soil sampling (see above section). A total of 16 plots for deadwood estimation was laid out (4 in Block 52, 7 in Block 97, 3 in 142, 1 in Block 214 and 1 in Block 146, see Table 12.3).

The procedure for measuring deadwood was like the Danish NFI (Alban et al. 2023). In terms of lying deadwood, only pieces at least 1 m long and 10 cm thick on the middle would be incorporated. In terms of standing deadwood, diameter would have to be at least 40 cm to be counted in the 15 m radius circle, if between 10 and 40 then it is counted in the 10 m radius circle. Sampling points are marked with false acacia sticks. The degradation stage and species of the deadwood was also noted (if recognizable).

Table 12.3 Coordinates for the deadwood sampling.

No	Name	Species	Plot	UTM_east (m)	UTM_north (m)	Dec_deg_north (°)	Dec_deg_east (°)
1	52_Plot_A_Stripe	Silver fir	A	521874.15	6216477.78	56.0929259	9.3515731
2	52_Plot_F_Stripe	Beech- silver fir	F	521909.87	6216634.34	56.0943309	9.3521601
3	52_Plot J	Beech- Norway spruce	J	522004.16	6216688.69	56.0948151	9.3536803
4	52_Plot K	Norway spruce	K	522126.41	6216473.17	56.0928729	9.3556269
5	97_B02	Silver fir- beech	11	521300.52	6215400.12	56.08327	9.342268
6	97_B03	Silver fir- beech	19	521400.09	6215400.05	56.083264	9.343868
7	97_C03	Douglas fir-beech	17	521400.1	6215300.8	56.082373	9.34386
8	97_B01	Silver fir	2	521200.64	6215400.39	56.083276	9.340663
9	97_A01	Beech- silver fir	4	521200.32	6215490.71	56.084088	9.340665
10	97_A02	Beech	12	521300.9	6215470.77	56.083904	9.342279
11	97_C04	Douglas fir-beech	24	521480.83	6215280.33	56.082185	9.345155
12	142_B01	Douglas fir-beech	D	519700.51	6215100.61	56.080647	9.316536
13	142_B02	Douglas fir-beech	F	519800.92	6215100.61	56.080643	9.31815
14	142_A03	Beech- Norway spruce	H	519902.94	6215300.22	56.082432	9.319804
15	214_A01	Beech	A (21)	517890.4	6215090.19	56.080625	9.287452
16	146	Douglas fir	A	522416.5	6214218.3	56.07260	9.36010

13 Status of the experiment at initiation of thinning (2024-2025)

Data was collected in the experiment from autumn 2024 to summer 2025.

13.1 Shelter density (overstorey density)

Table 13.1 shows the shelter density of plots across Block 52 in 2025. The effect of the original shelter categories can clearly be seen on the shelter density (dense plots generally have much higher shelter density).

Table 13.1 Shelter density and new plot area of plots in Block 52 in spring 2025. Original plot numbers are also listed since shelter density is calculated based on the original plot areas. This is because shelter density is calculated for the sum of the two original plots (which includes e.g. border areas) to allow comparison with previous shelter density estimates.

Block	Original plot no.	Original shelter category	Shelter density (m ² /ha) ^{***}	New plot name	New plot area (m ²) ^{**}
52	1	Dense	20.0	A	3333
52	16	Dense	12.2		
52	2	Dense	14.6	B	3215
52	15	Dense	13.3		
52	3	Dense	16.4	C	3468
52	14	Dense	13.2		
52	4	Dense	16.0	D	3366
52	13	Dense	13.1		
52	5	Dense	12.9	E	3489
52	6	Dense	14.1		
52	11	Dense	12.2	F	3442
52	12	Dense	13.9		
52	7	Dense	15.2	G	3513
52	10	Dense	15.4		
52	8	Dense	17.1	H	3417
52	9	Dense	14.8		
52	23	Medium	9.0	I	1735
52	24	Medium	4.9		
52	25	Medium	9.2	J	2249
52	26	Medium	3.2		
52	-	-*	0	K	2536

*Outside of original 1512 experiment.

** A corner pipe was missing in the GPS measurement for three plots (Plot A, F, and G), meaning that the area for these three plots is for now assessed based on estimation based on the three other pipes. Maximum deviation from this would be within a few square meters (plots are rectangular).

***Based on the original plot areas (original plots) from the original 1512 plots.

Table 13.2 Shelter density across plots of Block 142 in spring 2025E (both according to the original and the new plot delineation).

Block	Original plot	Shelter category	Shelter density (m ² /ha)*	New plot	New plot area (m ²)
142	1	Dense	10.0	A	2926
142	2	Dense	15.1		
142	3	Dense	22.6	B	2842
142	4	Dense	15.9		
142	15	Dense	15.4	D	2947
142	16	Dense	14.0		
142	17	Medium	7.0	E	2950
142	18	Medium	14.3		
142	31	Medium	18.9	F	3173
142	32	Medium	8.1		
142	40	Open	5.3	G	3710
142	41	Open	10.2	H	2358
142	46	Open	0.0	I	1432
142	34	Open	6.9	J	3056
142	47	Open	6.8		
142	33	Open	11.4	K	3110
142	48	Open	8.1		

*Generally based on the original plot areas (original plots) from the original 1512 plots. Note that there seems to be minor deviations in the plot size for many plots in Block 142 in the original establishment report.

**Based on the main plot area in the new experiment (had not been measured before).

Table 13.3: Plots in Block 146.

Block	Original Plot	New plot	Shelter category	Plot area (m ²)	Shelter density (m ² /ha)
146	-	A	-	1717	0
146	-	B	-	2855	0

Table 13.4: Plots in Block 214

Block	Original Plot	Shelter density (m ² /ha)*	New plot	Shelter category	New plot area (m ²)
214	20	1.6	A	Light	2649
214	21	1.6			
214	19	16.9	B	Light	3146
214	22	19.6			

*Calculated from the original plot areas from Brunner et al. (2005) as this also included border areas.

Table 13.5: Plots in Block 97.

Block	Original /new plot	Shelter category	Shelter density, 2025 before thinning (m ² /ha)*	Shelter density, 2025, after thinning (m ² /ha)*	New plot area (m ²)
97	1	Dense	27.2	13.6	2884
97	2	Dense	21.8	13.2	2952
97	3	Dense	23.6	13.8	2293
97	4	Dense	33.5	24.7	1646
97	5	Dense	36.7	22.4	1695
97	6	Dense	26.0	18.0	2070
97	7	Dense	17.2	17.2	1860
97	8	Dense	28.6	19.2	1549
97	10	Medium	17.4	13.2	2547
97	11	Medium	17.4	9.7	2383
97	12	Medium	27.8	17.1	2322
97	14	Medium	15.9	8.5	2483
97	15	Medium	18.2	9.2	2627
97	16	Medium	22.0	11.0	2498
97	17	Open	16.4	9.0	1816
97	18	Open	14.9	8.3	2263
97	19	Open	17.5	8.0	2071
97	20	Open	24.5	11.6	1637
97	21	Open	21.5	12.0	1706
97	22	Open	12.7	6.9	2524
97	24	Open	17.8	9.4	1848

*Calculated from the original plot areas from Brunner et al. (2005) as this also included border areas.

13.2 Understorey

13.2.1 General patterns

Stand data for Block 52 indicates that this block is a suitable area for a mixed forest experiment (Table 13.6). Development stage is very similar across the different plots, only plot K is a bit more developed than the other plots. Surprisingly, the stem number was 5262 stems/ha before thinning in plot I in Block 52. This is well above the initial planting density of beech (4000 stems/ha). This may either be due to a mistake in the GPS measurement of this block (resulting in multiplication with a wrong area factor), or that the planting density in some points of this block has been considerably larger than planned.

In contrast, stand data for Block 142 (Table 13.7) illustrates that this block has larger within-block variation than Block 52, especially among the Douglas fir-beech plots which vary very much from east to west. While the silver fir plot is even a bit lower than silver fir in Block 52 ($H_g=4.4$ m), the most developed Douglas fir areas plots have $H_g > 12$ m.

Stand data was rather different between the two Douglas fir plots after thinning (Table 13.8). Basal area was 12.7 m²/ha in the crop tree thinning, relative to 8.7 m²/ha in the thinning from below treatment and D_g was also substantially larger in A, as a consequence of the slower development in the northern part (further exemplified by the within-plot variation in crop tree development in Table 13.14).

Table 13.6: Stand data for plots in Block 52 in spring 2025. BS = percentage bark stripped. BA=basal area. Vol.=volume. BS = percentage bark stripped. N. spruce=Norway spruce. Sum includes only the mentioned target species.

Plot	Thinning	Species	Before thinning						Thinning				After thinning					
			N/ha	BA (m ² /ha)	Dg (cm)	Hg (m)	Vol. (m ³ /ha)	BS%	N/ha	BA (m ² /ha)	Dg (cm)	Vol. (m ³ /ha)	N/ha	BA (m ² /ha)	Dg (cm)	Hg (m)	Vol. (m ³ /ha)	BS%
A*	From below	Silver fir	2631	8.0	6.2	5.2	36	100	444	0.5	3.8	2	2187	7.5	6.6	5.4	33	100
B	Crop tree	Silver fir	2557	7.6	6.2	5.2	34	96	128	0.4	6.4	2	2429	7.2	6.1	5.2	32	96
C	From below	Silver fir	1995	5.7	6.0	5.1	25	96	190	0.2	4.0	1	1805	5.5	6.2	5.2	24	96
		Beech	998	0.5	2.5	3.5	3	3	52	0.0	1.2	0	946	0.5	2.6	3.6	3	3
		Sum	2993	6.2	5.1	-	28	-	242	0.2	3.5	1	2750	6	-	-	27	-
D	Crop tree	Silver fir	1607	5.7	6.7	5.0	25	100	137	0.6	7.7	3	1471	5.0	6.6	5.0	22	100
		Beech	808	0.7	3.4	3.9	4	0	12	0.0	6.4	0	796	0.7	3.3	3.8	4	0
		Sum	2415	6.4	5.8	-	29	-	149	0.7	7.6	3	2267	5.7	-	-	26	-
E	Crop tree	Beech	851	2.5	6.2	5.8	15	0	80	0.4	7.7	1	1892	2.5	4.1	6.0	14	0
		Silver fir	2006	2.8	4.2	6.1	11	100	115	0.3	5.4	2	771	2.2	6.0	5.7	10	100
		Sum	2857	5.3	4.9	-	26	-	195	0.6	6.5	3	2663	4.7	-	-	23	-
F*	From below	Beech	1897	2.5	4.1	5.4	14	2	116	0.1	4.5	0	1781	2.4	4.2	5.5	13	2
		Silver fir	979	2.9	6.1	4.7	13	87	142	0.2	2.4	1	837	2.6	6.3	4.8	12	87
		Sum	2876	5.4	4.9	-	27	-	259	0.3	3.7	1	2618	5.1	-	-	25	-
G*	Crop tree	Beech	2556	3.4	4.1	5.7	18	0	139	0.3	5.4	2	2417	3.1	4.0	5.6	16	0
H	From below	Beech	3269	4.5	4.2	6.3	25	0	331	0.2	2.9	1	2938	4.2	4.3	6.4	24	0
I	Crop tree	Beech	4542	6.9	4.4	6.2	38	1	231	0.6	5.7	3	4311	6.3	4.3	6.2	35	1
J	Crop tree	Beech	3397	6.6	5.0	6.1	36	1	449	1.1	5.5	6	2948	5.6	4.9	6.0	30	1
		N. spruce	2343	5.3	5.4	5.0	20	9	711	1.7	5.5	6	1632	3.6	5.3	5.0	14	11
		Total	5740	11.9	5.1	-	56	-	1161	2.8	5.5	12	4580	9.2	-	-	44	-
K	Crop tree	N. spruce	5524	20.0	6.8	6.8	94	100	883	2.7	6.3	12	4641	17.2	6.9	6.8	82	100

* Stand data for plot A, F and G are based on estimates for the plot area (see Table 13.1) – not precise GPS measurement. Deviations should be small.

Table 13.7: Stand data for plots in Block 142 in spring 2025, before and after thinning. BA=basal area. Vol.=volume. BS = percentage bark stripped. N. spruce=Norway spruce. Sum includes only the mentioned target species.

Plot	Thinning	Species	Before thinning						Thinning				After thinning					
			N/ha	BA (m ² /ha)	Dg (cm)	Hg (m)	Vol. (m ³ /ha)	BS%	N/ha	BA (m ² /ha)	Dg (cm)	Vol. (m ³ /ha)	N/ha	BA (m ² /ha)	Dg (cm)	Hg (m)	Vol. (m ³ /ha)	BS%
A	From below	Douglas fir	1367	9.7	9.5	8.7	53	19	314	0.5	4.6	2	1052	9.2	10.5	9.5	51	17
		Beech	550	0.5	3.4	5.8	3	0	0	0	-	-	550	0.5	3.4	5.8	3	0
		Sum	1917	10.2	-	-	56	-	314	0.5	-	2	1603	9.7	-	-	54	-
B	Crop tree	Silver fir	3184	6.5	5.1	4.4	29	93	598	1.5	5.6	6	2586	5.1	5.0	4.3	23	92
D	Crop tree	Douglas fir	1513	12.5	10.2	9.8	76	33	465	4.1	10.6	25	1049	8.4	10.1	9.7	51	30
		Beech	702	1.3	4.8	5.3	8	3	254	0.5	5.1	3	448	0.8	4.6	5.1	5	2
		Sum	2215	13.7	-	-	84	-	719	4.6	-	28	1496	9.1	-	-	56	-
E	Crop tree	Douglas fir	1525	15.2	11.3	11.4	101	25	600	5.3	10.6	34	925	9.9	11.7	11.7	67	22
		Beech	905	2.7	6.1	9.4	19	2	376	1.0	5.8	7	529	1.7	6.3	9.5	12	2
		Sum	2431	17.9	-	-	119	-	976	6.3	-	41	1454	11.6	-	-	78	-
F	From below	Douglas fir	1494	17.4	12.2	11.7	116	19	870	6.9	10.0	42	624	10.6	14.7	13.1	75	9
		Beech	908	3.8	7.3	8.3	25	3	274	0.5	5.0	3	633	3.2	8.1	8.8	22	3
		Sum	2402	21.2	-	-	142	-	1144	7.4	-	45	1257	13.8	-	-	97	-
G	Crop tree	Beech	2210	5.9	5.8	6.6	37	3	472	1.5	6.3	9	1739	4.4	5.7	6.5	27	3
		N. spruce	3353	8.6	5.7	6.6	42	99	1337	3.0	5.4	14	2016	5.5	5.9	6.8	28	99
		Sum	5563	14.4	-	-	79	-	1809	4.5	-	23	3755	9.9	-	-	56	-
H	Crop tree	Beech	2723	13.6	7.9	9.1	97	2	606	3.8	8.9	28	2116	9.8	7.7	8.9	70	3
I	Crop tree	N. spruce	6271	32.2	8.1	8.0	165	94	1606	9.7	8.8	50	4665	22.5	7.8	7.9	115	92
J	Crop tree	Douglas fir	1384	22.0	14.2	13.4	162	2	546	9.0	14.5	66	838	13.0	14.1	13.3	96	2
		Beech	582	4.2	9.6	11.7	34	1	223	1.6	9.7	13	360	2.6	9.6	11.6	21	1
		Sum	1967	26.3	-	-	196	-	769	10.7	-	79	1198	15.6	-	-	117	-
K	From below	Douglas fir	1611	22.8	13.4	12.0	159	18	997	9.9	11.2	61	614	12.9	16.4	14.1	97	7
		Beech	894	4.2	7.7	11.7	35	5	383	1.3	6.6	11	511	2.8	8.4	12.1	24	5
		Sum	2505	27.0	-	-	194	-	1379	11.2	-	72	1125	15.8	-	-	121	-

Table 13.8: Stand data for plots in Block 146 (both pure Douglas fir). BS = percentage bark stripped.

New plot	Thinning	Thinning								After thinning					
		Species removal*			Douglas fir stem number reduction				All reduction	N/ha	Dg (cm)	Hg (m)	BA (m ² /ha)	Vol. (m ³ /ha)	BS %
		BA (m ² /ha)	N/ha	Dg (cm)	BA (m ² /ha)	N/ha	Dg (cm)	Vol (m ³ /ha)	% basal area removed**						
A	For crop trees	-	-	-	8.2	711	12.1	55	34	1386	12.0	12.3	15.6	105	77
B	From below	6.0	2487	5.5	0.0	-	-	-	32	2161	8.7	8.6	12.9	71	49

*Other species than Douglas fir, mostly Norway spruce and larch, see 11.4.1.

** Both species removal and Douglas fir stem number reduction.

13.2.2 Thinning intensity and pattern

Across both Block 52 and 142, crop-tree thinning was generally heavier than thinning from below (Tables 13.8–13.9).

In Block 142, mean basal area removal reached 33 % under crop-tree thinning versus 25 % for thinning from below, corresponding to a C-grade (heavy) thinning in Danish terminology. The intensity was greatest in the most developed Douglas fir–beech mixtures and lowest in the least developed plots which was not surprisingly the silver fir plot. On average 33 % of Douglas fir basal area was thinned, while only 23% of silver fir basal area was thinned.

There is a clear tendency in the thinning intensity between the two treatments. In the least developed plots, thinning from below is less intense compared to crop tree thinning. On plots that are more developed, thinning from below starts to be as intense as the Crop tree thinning. In Block 52, thinning was much weaker overall (due to slower development), especially regarding thinning from below, while crop-tree thinning of was relatively heavier (the only exception is for unexplained reasons the pure silver fir plots). This reflects the targeted removal pattern around selected crop trees, rather than uniform basal area removal, removing competitors even when Hg is not very high (remember also that the crop tree thinning was weaker implemented in Block 52).

The calculated RTD (RTD ≈ 0.22–0.24, see section 11.5) for thinning in Block 142 corresponded to a very heavy thinning in spatial terms. However, basal area removal values in Block 142 indicate only moderate to heavy (C-grade) intensity. This difference arises because thinning removed many small and suppressed trees, strongly increasing spacing without removing much basal area. The first thinning in these dense young stands therefore mainly reduced competition structurally rather than volumetrically. Similar comparison could also be made for Block 52 (with even more pronounced results) but less interesting because thinning would not normally have been conducted in a stand at this development stage.

Thinning quotients further illustrate this pattern. In Block 52, thinning from below had low quotients (average 0.71), while crop-tree thinning averaged 1.22, indicating selective removal of smaller stems versus retention of larger individuals. In Block 142, quotients between the two thinning types resembled each other more due to more advanced development (probably due to less stand differentiation), but thinning from below was still generally well below 1 (apart from beech in K).

Absolute basal area removed on the two plots in 146 were almost similar (Table 13.8) although the nature of the removal (Species, Dg) was very different.

Table 13.9 Overview of thinning intensity (percentage of basal area thinned) and thinning quotient across Block 52 (percentage of basal area thinned) across plots in Block 52. Thinning quotient is defined as Dg of thinned trees divided by Dg before thinning. BA= basal area. SF = silver fir, NS=Norway spruce. T_{avr} =average thinning.

Plot	A		B		C			D			E			F			G	H	I	J			K	
Thinning	From below		Crop tree		From below			Crop tree			Crop tree			From below			Crop tree	From below	Crop tree	Crop tree			Crop tree	
Species	SF		SF		SF Beech		T _{avr}	SF Beech		T _{avr}	Beech SF		T _{avr}	Beech SF		T _{avr}	Beech	Beech	Beech	Beech NS		T _{avr}	NS	
BA thinned (%)	6		5		4 1		4	11 5		10	9 15		12	2 8		5	10	5	9	16 32		23	13	
Thinning quotient	0.68		1.08		0.67 0.50		-	1.18 1.93		-	1.30 1.31		-	0.76 0.59		0.78	1.35	0.70	1.40	1.17 1.03		-	0.91	

Table 13.10 Overview of thinning intensity (percentage of basal area thinned) and thinning quotient across plots in Block 142. Calculated using the estimates rounded to the first decimal from Table 13.7. BA= basal area, DF =Douglas fir, SF = silver fir, NS=Norway spruce. T_{avr} =average thinning.

Plot	A			B	D			E			F			G			H	I	J			K			
Thinning	From below			Crop tree	Crop tree			Crop tree			From below			Crop tree			Crop tree	Crop tree	Crop tree			From below			
Species	DF Beech		T _{avr}	SF	DF Beech		T _{avr}	DF Beech		T _{avr}	DF Beech		T _{avr}	Beech NS		T _{avr}	Beech	NS	DF Beech		T _{avr}	DF Beech		T _{avr}	
BA thinned (%)	5 0		5	23	33 38		34	35 37		35	40 13		35	25 35		31	28	30	41 38		41	43 31		41	
Thinning quotient	0.55		-	-	1.13		1.14 1.13	-	1.03 0.98		-	0.88 0.72		-	1.11 0.83		-	1.16	1.10	1.09 1.09		1.09	0.89 1.01		-

13.2.3 Non-target species removal

Basal area of non-target species was generally low before the measurement/thinning (< 0.1 m²/ha; Table 13.11), reflecting that most of the non-target species had already been removed before the stands was measured (see section 11.4.2.1). Minor residual basal areas remained on a few plots (notably 52 I, J, K and 142 G, I) primarily consisting of **natural regeneration of Norway spruce** and occasional larch, Scots pine or silver fir. Some of these also remained after the measurement/thinning (to avoid large open spaces in the stands).

Table 13.11: Basal area of other species than the target species at plots in Block 52 and 142 – before, thinned and after thinning. Plots not represented on the table had no other species present. Recall that the thinning of other species listed on this table is just the remaining parts of other species on the plots (most of the other species had been removed before the stand was measured, see 11.4.2.1).

Block	Plot	Before thinning/measurement		Thinning		After thinning/measurement	
		Basal area (m ² /ha)	Species	Basal area (m ² /ha)	Species	Basal area (m ² /ha)	Species
52	A	0.08	Larch, Norway spruce, Sitka spruce, Scots pine.	0.04	Larch, Norway spruce, Sitka spruce, Scots pine.	0.04	Remaining: larch, Norway spruce and Sitka spruce
52	B	0.08	Larch, Scots pine, Sitka spruce	0.02	Sitka spruce	0.07	Larch, Scots pine, Sitka spruce
52	C	0.04	Sitka spruce	0.04	Sitka spruce	0.00	-
52	D	0.01	Norway spruce	0.00	-	0.01	Norway spruce
52	E	0.02	Sitka spruce	0.00	-	0.02	Sitka spruce
52	G	0.05	Norway spruce	0.00	-	0.05	Norway spruce
52	I	0.34	Scots pine, Norway spruce	0.21	Scots pine, Norway spruce	0.13	Norway spruce
52	J	0.17	Scots pine	0.17	Scots pine	0.00	-
52	K	0.43	Silver fir, Sitka spruce, Scots pine	0.04	Silver fir	0.39	Silver fir, Sitka spruce, Scots pine
142	A	0.02	Silver fir, Norway spruce	0.01	-	0.02	-
142	G	0.20	Mainly silver fir	0.03	Silver fir	0.17	Silver fir
142	I	0.17	Silver fir and Scots pine	0.00	Silver fir	0.17	Silver fir and Scots pine
142	K	0.02	Birch	0.02	Birch	0.00	-

13.2.4 Crop tree characteristics

In Block 52 (Table 13.12), crop-tree heights ranged 6.2–7.7 m for beech and 6.4–6.8 m for silver fir, while Norway spruce crop trees were clearly taller (8.3–9.8 m). Bark stripping was virtually absent in beech, variable in spruce, and universal (100 %) in silver fir crop trees.

As for the stand data, crop trees in Block 142 (Table 13.13) also exhibits greater variation linked to the former shelterwood conditions, with mean species-specific crop-tree DBH differences of 4 cm and average height differences of 3 and 5 m across plots among Douglas fir and beech respectively. Especially beech shows unexpectedly high between-plot height variation, likely associated with browsing effects in the conifer-dominated environment (keeping them grazed down under the denser shelter, where it has taken longer to get above browsing height compared to in the east/under open shelter).

In Block 146 (Table 13.14), the two pure Douglas fir plots show similar development to mixed Douglas fir–beech plots in Block 142 with the same thinning, though plot B (thinning from below) contains a few smaller individuals, reflecting its delineation principle rather than treatment effect. The pure Douglas plot B in Block 146 (thinning from below) has similar crop trees to the mixed Douglas fir-beech plot A in Block 142. Crop trees in the pure Douglas fir plot A in Block 146 (thinning for crop trees) have quite similar development to Douglas fir in the mixed plots E and J in Block 142.

Table 13.12 Data for potential future crop trees in Block 52.

Plot	Thinning	Species	No	DBH (cm)	Height (m)	Crown height (m)	Crown diameter (m)	Defoliation (%)	Bark stripped (%)
A	From below	Silver fir	33	9.2	6.8	3.0	1.6	9	100
B	Crop tree	Silver fir	30	8.5	6.6	2.8	1.8	7	100
C	From below	Silver fir	27	8.5	6.4	2.8	1.5	8	100
		Beech	6	5.3	6.2	3.5	1.7	6	0
		Total	33	7.9	6.3	2.9	1.5	7	82
D	Crop tree	Silver fir	30	9.8	6.6	2.7	2.0	7	100
		Beech	8	7.2	6.6	3.5	1.9	6	0
		Total	38	9.3	6.6	2.9	2.0	6	79
E	Crop tree	Beech	27	7.0	6.9	3.3	2.1	3	0
		Silver fir	8	9.4	6.6	2.6	2.0	5	100
		Total	35	7.5	6.9	3.1	2.1	4	23
F	From below	Beech	23	6.6	7.0	3.8	1.6	5	4
		Silver fir	9	9.4	6.7	2.9	1.9	7	100
		Total	32	7.4	6.9	3.5	1.7	6	31
G	Crop tree	Beech	39	6.4	6.9	3.1	1.9	8	0
H	From below	Beech	39	6.8	7.2	3.7	1.6	6	0
I	Crop tree	Beech	24	7.8	7.7	3.8	1.7	5	0
J	Crop tree	Beech	26	8.3	7.4	3.2	1.9	8	0
		Norway spruce	12	11.2	8.3	2.7	2.6	7	8
		Total	38	9.2	7.7	3.0	2.1	8	3
K	Crop tree	Norway spruce	30	13.7	9.8	3.2	2.2	8	100

Table 13.13 Data for potential future crop trees in Block 142. Total stand is weighted by the number of observations/crop trees within each species (apart from for “No” where it is just the sum). Note that one Douglas fir crop tree is by mistake outside the plot in plot F. All bark stripping damages are original, except for one Douglas fir on plot F.

Plot	Thinning	Species	No.	DBH (cm)	Height (m)	Crown height (m)	Crown diameter (m)	Defoliation (%)	Bark stripped (%)
A	From below	Douglas fir	26	14.5	11.2	3.6	2.7	11	19
		Beech	5	8.5	7.8	3.6	2.0	5	0
		Total stand*	31	13.6	10.6	3.6	2.6	10	16
B	Crop tree	Silver fir	29	9.4	6.4	2.7	2.2	5	100
D	Crop tree	Douglas fir	24	14.9	12.7	4.0	3.6	11	8
		Beech	8	9.5	10.4	4.2	2.7	4	0
		Total	32	13.5	11.9	4.1	3.4	9	6
E	Crop tree	Douglas fir	22	16.5	13.6	3.6	4.7	14	0
		Beech	11	9.2	10.4	3.9	2.6	5	0
		Total	33	14.1	12.5	3.7	4.0	11	0
F	From below	Douglas fir	23	17.3	14.1	4.4	5.4	7	4
		Beech	11	12.1	10.5	5.2	3.5	5	0
		Total	33	15.6	12.8	4.7	4.8	6	3
G	Crop tree	Beech	22	10.0	8.9	4.1	2.2	8	0
		Norway spruce	15	10.2	9.5	2.4	3.1	8	100
		Total	37	10.1	9.1	3.4	2.5	8	41
H	Crop tree	Beech	23	12.3	11.0	5.1	2.4	4	0
I	Crop tree	Norway spruce	15	16.6	11.1	3.3	3.8	6	100
J	Crop tree	Douglas fir	22	18.2	14.9	3.9	5.9	8	0
		Beech	11	12.3	12.0	5.3	3.6	6	0
		Total	33	16.2	13.9	4.4	5.1	8	0
K	From below	Douglas fir	24	18.8	15.2	3.5	6.2	12	0
		Beech	12	11.0	13.1	3.9	4.0	4	8
		Total	36	16.2	14.5	3.6	5.5	9	3

Table 13.14 Data for potential future crop trees in Block 146. Parenthesis denotes min and max values for DBH and Height.

New plot	Thinning	No	DBH (cm)	Height (m)	Crown height (m)	Crown diameter (m)	Defoliation (%)	Bark stripped (%)
A	For crop trees	16	18.1 (13.9-21.9)	14.3 (11.5-16.0)	4.7	4.9	8	38
B	From below	34	13.7 (5.7-21.6)	11.3 (4.7-15.6)	3.0	3.8	11	35

13.2.5 Early mixed forest effects?

Does the data already indicate a mixed forest effect? This is most easily investigated by using before-thinning data of plots A-H in Block 52, where the shelter density is quite homogeneous (and has been so for the last 25 years). Based on this data (compiled in Table 13.15), no mixed forest effects in terms of overyielding are apparent. It makes sense that such effects, if present, would not reveal themselves until after the overstorey has been removed and the stand has developed further.

Table 13.15 Actual vs expected standing volume of the understorey across mixing gradients under dense shelter in Block 52.

Species	Actual standing volume (m ³ /ha)	Expected Standing volume (m ³ /ha)
Silver fir	35	35
Silver fir-beech	29	30
Beech-silver fir	26	25
Beech	21	21

13.3 Deadwood

The quantity of deadwood varied among the blocks of the experiments (Table 13.16). Two blocks (146 and 214) included no deadwood at all, while Block 52 and 142 had some lying deadwood (<7 m³/ha). Block 97 contained much more deadwood, due to recent bark beetle outbreak in this compartment.

Table 13.16 The quantity of lying and standing deadwood on the 14 plots.

Deadwood	52	97	142	146	214
Lying (m ³ /ha)	3.6	20.1	6.7	0	0
Standing (m ³ /ha)	0	12.2	0	0	0

14 Future activities

The experiment should expectedly be measured and thinned every 4 or 5 years, next time in spring 2029 or 2030. Importantly, the 1 m thinning around crop trees in Block 52 should be conducted more consistently than was done in 2025 and should likely be carried out even earlier than after 4 or 5 years. It is also important to initiate thinning treatment in Block 214 and 97 by 2030 or whenever the need arises.

As mentioned in the introductory chapters, stem quality in mixture vs. monoculture might be relevant as a future focus. Care should be taken when comparing the beech (in 142) and Douglas fir (146) with the mixture of Douglas fir-beech in 142. For pure Douglas fir, the planting density was lower than for the mixture. For pure beech, while the planting density was in principle like that of the mixture, the density was effectively lower because 1/3 of the stand (silver fir) basically died following the shelter loss in 2005. Somewhat similar problems are present for the Norway spruce-beech species combinations.

Apart from the trees and stand variables measured so far, biodiversity data should also be collected in the future and compared with the data from reference plantations nearby. The surroundings to all the blocks are still dense Norway spruce plantations established in the same year as the experiment was, providing a setting for comparing the biodiversity between different target species combinations in the conversion as well as with reference plantations.

The experiment is expected to continue until the end of the rotation of the underplanted plots.

15 References

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16 Appendix

16.1 Original experimental blocks from former Experiment 1512.

Figure 16.1 Overview original Experiment 1512. Experimental layout of a) Block 52, b) Block 142, c) Block 97 and d) Block 214. Pine weevil treatment is not included on the visualization as there was no effect of this treatment. Visualizations are translated directly from Brunner et al. (2005).

16.2 Soil conditions.

Table 16.1 and Table 16.2 shows the overall soil conditions across the different blocks. Indication of a moist and very nutrient poor soil was also given by the high coverage of cranberries in Block 97 in 2024. Texture variables will be made but the analysis of them was belated, and they were not available at the time of the writing of this report. Specific soil chemistry across the gradient in species combinations for Block 52 is shown on Table 16.3.

Table 16.1 Soil conditions across the five blocks of the experiments. Assessed through soil samples near each corner and in the center of each block (for 142 it was only assessed for at central western and eastern part of the Douglas fir/ beech area and for 146 it was only assessed from one central point). Soil variables refer to the 0-90 cm depth of soil, with average values based on samples taken at 0–30, 30–60 and 60–90 cm depth near each corner and in the center of each block. Parentheses indicate topsoil properties (0–30 cm).

Block	pH	CN	Texture
52	4.1	30.8 (30.0)	
97	4.0	26.8 (28.3)	
142	3.7	34.1 (39.1)	
146			
214	4.0	32.5 (31.4)	

Table 16.2 Soil horizon descriptions for the upper 1 m soil across the four original blocks of 1512 (for the central soil pit dug in each block). "(m)" refers to cemented layers. Conducted by Ditlev Otto Juel Reventlow in 2019. Color codes refer to Munsell soil color charts.

52 (01.09.2019)			97 (24.03.2019)		142 (30.08.2019)		214 (25.03.2019)	
	Depth (cm)	Color	Depth (cm)	Color	Depth (cm)	Color	Depth (cm)	Color
O	0-4	7.5 YR 2.5/1	0-15	2.5 YR 2.5/1	0-13	7.5 YR 2.5/1	0-12	10 YR 2/1
A	4-14	7.5 YR 2.5/1	-		13-19	7.5 YR 3/1	-	-
E	14-20	7.5 YR 2.5/1	15-30	2.5 YR 5/1	19-28	7.5 YR 5/1	12-26	10 YR 5/1
Bh	20-33	7.5 YR 2.5/1	30-37	2.5 YR 2.5/1	28-33	7.5 YR 2.5/1	26-29	10 YR 2/1
Bs (m)	33-45	7.5 YR 2.5/1	37-50	10 YR 5/8	-	7.5 YR 2.5/3	29-60	Varying
BS	45-64	7.5 YR 4/6	50-100	2.5 YR 5/4	33-81	7.5 YR 5/6	60-100	10 YR 2/1
C	64-100	7.5 YR 6/3	-		Beyond auger		-	
Comments	Hard layer in Bs (m) layer. Many stones in the profile		Very few stones. Cemented layer is not very hard. Most roots in top 15 cm.		Soil auger sample. Does not appear as cemented as other blocks. Not many stones		More stones, roots and cementation compared to 97	

Table 16.3 Soil chemistry across species combinations in Block 52 in 2025 (Douglas fir in Block 146).

Species	Depth	pH	CN	C	N
Silver fir	0-30	3.3	28.8	4.5	0.16
	30-60	4.0	25.3	1.2	0.04
	60-90	4.6		0.2	0.00
Silver fir-beech	0-30	3.3	32.5	4.2	0.13
	30-60	4.0	26.6	1.2	0.05
	60-90	4.6	18.4	0.3	0.01
Beech-silver fir	0-30	3.9	32.5	3.8	0.12
	30-60	3.9	29.9	0.6	0.02
	60-90	4.7	31.4	0.2	0.00
Beech	0-30	3.7	30.4	3.5	0.12
	30-60	4.0	30.8	0.8	0.03
	60-90	4.5	20.3	0.2	0.01
Beech-Norway spruce	0-30	3.4	32.1	4.4	0.14
	30-60	4.1	30.9	0.8	0.03
	60-90	4.6		0.1	0.00
Norway spruce	0-30	3.1			
	30-60	3.6	34.6	1.9	0.06
	60-90			0.4	0.00
Norway spruce (overstorey)	0-30	3.3	31.1	4.6	0.15
	30-60	3.9	30.0	0.7	0.02
	60-90	4.2	28.5	1.0	0.03
Douglas fir	0-30	3.2	35.4	3.8	0.11
	30-60	4.0	31.8	0.9	0.03
	60-90	4.6		0.1	0.00

16.3 Elaboration on provenances for Norway spruce and Douglas fir

16.3.1 Norway spruce

The provenance of the Norway spruce in Block 142 was Forsøgsvæsenet, while in Block 52 it was Forsts planteskole. Thus, the exact provenance is unsure, but they should be relatively similar in terms of growth (it is in any case not too important since the provenance effect here will be confounded with the block effect, e.g. slight differences in site conditions that are present between Block 52 and 142).

The pure Norway spruce replicate in Block 52 (but situated just outside the border of 52) was originally a planting of one row Norway of the provenance Palsgaard F.502 (2/2) and one row of silver fir of the provenance Gariglone, Iscritto al n.120 (2/1s), however the silver fir soon perished following shelter loss. Both were planted in 2001. The areas where there had previously been silver fir then filled up with natural regeneration of the overstorey (meaning of the provenance Forsts planteskole). It is worth noting that the Palsgaard provenance does not represent selectively bred material. Thus, as growth differences across Norway spruce provenance are generally small, the effects of this are expected to be negligible (furthermore, the pure Norway spruce in Block 142 was entirely the same provenance as in the mixture and monoculture).

16.3.2 Elaboration on Douglas fir in Block 146

Provenance of Douglas fir in both blocks of original 1512 was Lavereantiere B5456 (also named Lavercantiere FP323, French seed stand originating from Darrington, Washington seed zone 403 below 450m altitude, USA). The provenance in 146 was from the Olympic peninsula, Washington B2702 from Hoquiam seed zone 30 (0-150 m altitude). According to Larsen et al. (1997), Olympic peninsula provenances are considered to show fast growth. It could be speculated if the Hoquiam might be slightly faster growing due to a more coastal origin than Darrington. Comparison between Olympic peninsula provenances and provenances from Snoqualmie (located right next to Darrington) does however show very similar height growth (Lundberg 1957).

16.4 Procedure for laying out the thinning treatments

16.4.1 Laying out thinning treatments

In Block 142 and 52 (where the plots were relatively small and there in the original 1512 was a replicate due to the pine weevil treatment) thinning treatments were laid over two existing plots. This was also done for what remained in Block 214.

In Block 97, there were no replicates, but individual plots were so large (on average 2640 m²), that plots did not have to be merged in order to install thinning treatments.

Within the species combination, it was first identified where the conditions were most similar (typically using the 2019 data). Using this information, thinning treatments were laid out to ensure that the two thinning treatments were laid out on two areas that resembled each other as much as possible (in terms of basal area of overstorey and height growth and mortality of the underplanted species). Thinning treatments are then randomly assigned to the two resulting areas.

If no species combination made apparently more sense than the other based on the available data, then treatments were put across soil scarification treatment to avoid systematic biases from this.

16.4.2 Positioning of new thinning treatments within experiment

The following criteria were used in order of priority to determine how to put new experimental treatments:

1: Tree height is reasonably similar between treatments within planting modules: The average height within each of the new treatments within a particular planting module should be roughly the same. By roughly the same, we mean that the mean height of the trees measured within the original two net plots of each new treatment should be no more than 1 m different. It was furthermore checked in the field that the information from the net plots was valid on the rest of the plot area outside the net plot.

This rule was never violated whenever there was net plot data from 2019 but ended up being violated in Block 146 and for Norway spruce between the Norway spruce and beech-Norway spruce mixture in Block 52 and for beech between Beech and Beech-Norway spruce in Block 142.

2: Tree height is reasonably similar within plots composing new treatment: A difference of 1 m in average height growth across plots (based on net plot height in 2019) incorporated in the new treatments was the maximum difference in height growth allowed. It was furthermore checked in the field that the information from the net plots was valid on the rest of the plot area outside the net plot.

This rule was mainly violated in Block 146 where plot B had a substantial height variation from south to north.

Criteria 1 and 2 are to some degree in competition with each other in relation to where the exact treatments should be laid out, but criteria 1 was always given the highest priority to ensure that starting conditions between the two new emerging treatments were as similar as possible.

16.5 Thinning procedure in 2024/2025

Table 16.4 Planned harvesting in the different plots that are thinned in 2024/2025. The stem number reduction cannot easily be quantified for plot managed with thinning for crop trees – thus, here it is just marked as N/A. RTD=Relative tree distance.

Block	Plot	RTD used in harvesting	Stem number after thinning	% of original planting number	Block	Plot	RTD used in harvesting	Stem number after thinning per parcel ha (per monokultur ha)	% of original planting number
52	A	0.28	3000	75	142	A	0.24	Douglas fir: 1023 (1535*) Beech: Ingen hugst	38
	B	N/A	N/A	N/A		B	N/A	N/A	N/A
	C	N/A	N/A	N/A		C	N/A	N/A	N/A
	D	0.28	3000	75		D	NA	N/A	N/A
	E	0.28	3000	75		E	NA	N/A	N/A
	F	N/A	N/A	N/A		F	0.22	Douglas fir: 705 (1057*) Beech: 600 (1800*)	Douglas fir: 25 Beech: 40
	G	N/A	N/A	N/A		G	N/A	N/A	N/A
	H	0.28	3000	75		H	N/A	N/A	N/A
	I	N/A	N/A	N/A		I	N/A	N/A	N/A
	J	N/A	N/A	N/A		J	N/A	N/A	N/A
	K	N/A	N/A	N/A		K	0.22	Douglas fir: 555 (828*) Beech: 500 (1500*)	Douglas fir: 21 Beech: 33
146	A	0.22	No thinning in DGR	N/A	146	B	N/A	N/A	N/A

* Estimated per hectare in monoculture. Unlike in Block 52, in Block 142 the thinning requirement was calculated by species — partly due to the greater development of Douglas fir compared to beech, and partly because the planting pattern was more species-separated here (4 rows of Douglas fir followed by 2 rows of beech) compared to the beech/silver fir mixtures in Block 52, where the species alternated row by row.

16.6 Measuring defoliation.

Defoliation was measured for all crop trees and height measurement trees according to ICP guidelines (Table 16.5). The “-1” code is given to trees which have e.g. been thinned or are missing. It is important to note that the defoliation measurement is conducted in comparison to a fully defoliated local reference tree.

Table 16.5: Defoliation measurements (taken directly from ICP Forests 2020).

Code	Description
0	0%
5	>0-5%
10	>5-10%
15	>10-15%
20	>15-20%
25	>20-25%
30	>25-30%
35	>30-35%
40	>35-40%
45	>40-45%
50	>45-50%
55	>50-55%

Code	Description
60	>55-60%
65	>60-65%
70	>65-70%
75	>70-75%
80	>75-80%
85	>80-85%
90	>85-90%
95	>90-95%
99	>95-100% (alive)
100	100% (standing dead)
-1	no assessment